

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Microfinance Institutions on the Sustainability of Small and Medium Enterprises in Zambia: A Case study of Lusaka's Mtendere East

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 13th Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) MFIs Service Accessibility SMEs Financial Performance SME Challenges</p>	<p>The purpose of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) on the sustainability of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Zambia, with a particular focus on Lusaka's Mtendere East. The study aimed at assessing the accessibility of MFI services to SMEs, analyze the effects of MFI support on the sustainable financial performance of SMEs and investigate the challenges faced by MFIs in rendering services to SMEs. A case study design employing a mixed quantitative approach was adopted, involving 30 different SMEs and one MFI selected via purposive sampling. Using a sample size of 30 different SMEs, Findings revealed that 53.3% of SMEs secured access to Microfinance Services relatively easy while 36.7% reported difficulty. This was further explained by the Chi-square test between distance and access ($\chi^2 = 17.45$, $df = 9$, $p = 0.0421$, $\Phi = 0.763$). SME Financial performance showed 93.3% operational improvements, with a significant to customer acquisition ($\chi^2 = 13.98$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.0029$, $\text{Cramér's } V = 0.694$). However, Regression ($R^2 = 0.008$, $p = 0.6373$) and ANOVA ($F = 0.464$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.633$) found no significant relationship between financial management practices and profit change. Major constraints identified included high interest rates, poor credit history and length loan processing. The study recommended streamlining loan procedures, integrating financial programs and strengthening institutional governance to MFI effectiveness and SME sustainability in Lusaka's Mtendere East.</p>

1. Introduction

We cannot overlook the role of small business ventures to all areas of society and according to the World Bank (2020), SMEs account for over 90% of businesses and more than 50% of employment globally. They play a major part in economic growth, job creation, innovation and poverty reduction. On the other hand, Microfinance institutions play an important role in expanding financial access for underserved communities by providing small loans, savings accounts and other services to low-income individuals who cannot meet traditional banking requirements. García-Pérez et al, (2020) in 2018 noted an approximate number of MFIs, 916, worldwide which covered 80% women and 65% rural residents. In Africa, SMEs make up 80% of employment on the continent stressing their role in job creation and poverty alleviation (African Development Bank, 2022). While program initiatives such as African small and medium enterprise Program and African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) positions MFIs as strategic partners in facilitating cross-border trade and enhancing business competitiveness.

In Zambia, SMEs make up more than 70% of employment and a large share of registered businesses. Despite this, many SMEs struggle to obtain credit because of collateral requirements, high lending rates, and limited financial literacy (Chisala & Chileshe, 2020; Saidi, 2024). Mwanza and Phiri (2020) noted the banking sector in Zambia to be risk-averse when dealing with SMEs with little or no credit history and only prioritized larger enterprises with established credit histories. To bridge this financial gap, the Micro-finance Regulation under the Banking and Financial Services Act Of 2006 were introduced, enabling Micro-finance Institutions (MFIs) to enhance financial inclusion (Bank of Zambia, 2023). In the wake of this, national strategies like the Vision 2030 and the National Financial Strategy II 2024 - 2028, aimed at expanding the access to finance using loan guarantee scheme, digital finance and mobile banking (Makina & Nyambe, 2021; Bank of Zambia, 2024). Technological innovations has rapidly streamlined service delivery within the Micro-finance sector, yet still persistent challenges remain.

Mtendere East, a peri-urban township within Lusaka District, is characterized by small-scale manufacturing, informal trading and service-oriented enterprises. The area represents a high population density, limited formal employment opportunities and a

predominance of micro and small-scale businesses. While in proximity to Lusaka’s commercial centers, Zambia’s administrative and commercial hub, it offers SMEs and entrepreneurs with market access. The presence of MFI in the area helps bridge the gap of traditional banking services which largely depend of collateral and reputable credit history. However, despite the presence of MFIs in Mtendere East, SMEs still face challenges in accessing credit due to lack of collateral, low financial literacy, poor financial documentation, high lending costs and mismatches between loan products and business needs. Given these characteristics this underscores the need to evaluate the effectiveness of Microfinance Institution on the Sustainability of Small and Medium Enterprises in Lusaka’s Mtendere East.

1.2 Problem Statement

Given the background we have established, microfinance institutions and small and medium enterprises as a collectively play an important role in society. Their strategic roles address to major problems in society such as poverty reduction, job creation, financial inclusion and economic growth. Small and medium enterprises in peri-urban of areas of Zambia such Lusaka’s Mtendere East, still face challenges in accessing microfinance services. Saidi (2024), noted high interest rates, non-flexible payment plans and a lack of tailored financial products hindered SME accessibility and limited business expansion. Additionally operational challenges within microfinance institutions such as resource inefficiency, regulatory compliance and limited outreach, excluded many SMEs (Chisala & Chileshe, 2020). Lastly, limited empirical evidence among SMEs of Mtendere East despite the presence of microfinance institutions in area. This gave way to evaluate the effectiveness of microfinance institutions on the sustainability of small and medium enterprises in Lusaka’s Mtendere East.

1.3 Research Objectives

1.3.1 General Objective

The main objective of the study is evaluating the effectiveness of microfinance institutions on the sustainability of small and medium enterprises: a case Lusaka’s Mtendere east.

1.3.2 Specific objectives

- To assess the accessibility of MFI services by SMEs in Lusaka’s Mtendere East.
- To analyze the effects of MFIs support on the financial performance of SMEs in Lusaka’s Mtendere East.
- To investigate the challenges MFIs encounter in rendering services to SMEs in Lusaka’s Mtendere East.

1.4 Research Questions

- Are MFI services accessible to SMEs in Lusaka’s Mtendere East?
- What are the effects of MFI support on the financial performance of SMEs in Lusaka’s Mtendere East?
- What challenges do MFI encounter when rendering services to SMEs in Lusaka’s Mtendere East?

1.5 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework illustrates microfinance services as the independent variable impacting three dependent variables: dependent variables which are accessibility of microfinance services, financial performance of SMEs and Challenges MFI encounter in rendering services . The summary of this is as shown in the figure below.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

1.6 Significance of the study

The significance of the study lies in its contribution to empirical knowledge on SMEs and MFIs in Lusaka's Mtendere East, its support for evidence-based policy refinement and its clarification of barriers affecting SME access to microfinance. It further strengthens recommendations for improving MFI service delivery, aligns microfinance interventions with national development goals such as poverty reduction and economic diversification and highlights key non-financial constraints including financial literacy and business informality to guide targeted capacity building for SME growth.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Accessibility of Microfinance Institution Services by Small and Medium Enterprises

Jalhare (2025), in India, carried out a qualitative study, which examined the influence of microfinance institutions on micro, small and medium enterprise financial accessibility using 30 secondary sources. Microfinance institutions were grouped into formal and informal providers, where it was revealed that formal and semi-formal institutions provided more flexible credit services especially in rural areas. The challenges identified included urban bias, high interest rates and limited financial literacy from borrowers. The study's key recommendations were that of policy reforms aimed at reducing operational costs and improving outreach. Cull et al. (2022) and CGAP (2021), in similar findings, recommended institutional diversity among SMEs as well as regional customization. Burgees and Pandes (2005), stated poverty reduction through improved savings and credit provision as a result of rural banking expansion, at the same time warning informal microfinance institutions that did not have resources as formal banks.

Burki et al. (2018), in Pakistan conducted a study to determine the relationship between institutional characteristics and operational self-sufficiency among 25 microfinance institutions, using a panel and regression analysis. Their findings found that microfinance institutions with larger operational institutions, more years as well as a higher portion of female borrowers demonstrated better repayment performance and cost efficiency. The study recommended institutional diversity and gender inclusive lending as a well off enhancing accessibility and outreach. Borrower discipline and experienced managerial staff resulted in microfinance stability (Hartarska et al, 2006; Kinde, 2012).

Chikhaoui and Sobczak (2021) studied 12 microfinance institutions in Morocco and found that better rules and stronger oversight helped them reach more clients and stay financially stable. In Egypt, Mahmoud and Hassan (2023) tracked small businesses over time and saw that while loans helped these businesses grow, many still needed guidance and financial skills to keep doing well. Soliman (2020) also pointed out that digital tools, like mobile banking, make it easier for women to access money and run their businesses. Meanwhile, El Maghrebi, Alfitouri, and Salah (2022) showed that religious-based lending in Libya worked well for small businesses when backed by clear and steady rules. All of these studies show that access to finance depends on simple systems, strong support, and making sure business owners understand how to manage their money.

Phiri and Nkolola (2018) conducted a quantitative study involving 150 Lusaka based small and medium enterprises, the study employed a regression analysis and found that borrower education, financial training and prior repayment history significantly improved microfinance access. It recommended developing flexible loan terms and capacity building initiatives that are specifically tailored to small and medium enterprise needs. Saidi (2024) using a descriptive cross-sectional survey of 105 small and medium enterprises in Lusaka's central business district, discovered that high interest rates, collateral demands and complex application procedures limited access despite the importance of MFIs to small and medium enterprise growth. Similarly, Daka (2023) adopted a mixed-methods approach in Chazanga Compound and found that microfinance improved household income but was weakened by loan default risks and low financial literacy. Nyirenda et al. (2024) further observed that while technology and governance reforms improved access, institutional deficiencies and resource constraints persisted.

2.2 The Effects Of Microfinance Institution (MFIs) Support On The Performance Of Small And Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

Banerjee et al. (2015) conducted a study in India, Morocco and the Philippines, through six controlled randomized trials investigated over 4000 micro-borrowers in order to access the influence of microcredit on enterprise growth. Findings revealed that access to microfinance increased business investment and revenues by 10% within one year. However, high repayment pressure limited sustainability. The authors recommended integrated credit with financial training to enhance long term performance. Karlan and Zinman (2018) and Giné and Karlan (2018), reported similar findings, further, the authors suggesting bundle financial literacy programs improved repayment and strengthened business resilience. In contrast, Palanisamy and Parthasarathy (2015) argued that without supportive regulatory environments, the gains from microcredit remain short-lived.

Moussa (2020) conducted a study in Lebanon involving 17 small businesses supported by four microfinance institutions. Using regression and MANOVA, the study showed that microloans led to a 78% rise in net profit and a 93% change in the businesses' own resources, mainly influenced by loan size. The study recommended expanding access to rural areas and addressing gender gaps in lending. Revankar (2023) looked at 200 small entrepreneurs in India and found that microfinance led to an 18% increase in revenue and a 12% boost in profit margins, especially among those who received business coaching. Efendić and Hadžiahmetović (2017) focused on Bosnia and reported that microfinance helped create jobs and improved income stability for new businesses. On the other hand, Duçi et al. (2025) in Albania pointed out that while microfinance raised incomes, women still faced more obstacles than men when trying to access funding, which limited its overall impact.

Boukhechem and Hanifi (2019) studied the microfinance sector in Algeria and found that even with strong policies in place, too much bureaucracy made it hard for institutions to work efficiently. In Tunisia, Belkacem and Haoues (2023) looked at village banking in five farming communities using participatory tools. Their findings showed that peer support and group responsibility helped people repay loans on time and gave them better access to farming equipment. They recommended expanding this model to more rural areas. Chikhaoui and Sobczak (2021) also stressed that better supervision and stronger governance helped

microfinance institutions in Morocco become more stable and reach more clients. Meanwhile, in Japan, Tanaka and Suzuki (2025) found that while loans were available, the lack of follow-up advice after disbursement held back small business growth. They suggested that regular support after funding is just as important as the loan itself.

Mukendi and Manda (2022), in a study of women entrepreneurs supported by Vision Fund Zambia, found that access to microfinance improved group savings and cooperation, but limited business knowledge reduced long-term benefits. They recommended adding mentorship and basic training to strengthen the impact of microfinance support. Bwembya (2020) also highlighted that access to finance helped SMEs in Kitwe invest in better tools and technology, though growth was often held back by short-term loan conditions and high collateral demands. Kaulu et al. (2023) emphasized that business performance depended not just on financing but also on the owner's experience and financial skills. Meanwhile, Chitalu and Mwale (2022) noted that high operating costs and poor follow-up services made it harder for MFIs to support lasting SME growth, especially in peri-urban areas.

2.3 Challenges Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) Encounter in Rendering Services to Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

Clarke and Jones (2023) found that governance training helped boost SME turnover by 32% in UK Social Investment Tax Relief programs, but mismatches between tax incentives and borrower needs limited broader impact. They also noted the lack of standard metrics made it hard for MFIs to track social outcomes. Similarly, Peterson and Martinez (2021), studying CDFIs in the U.S. Midwest, showed that while credit access increased revenue and jobs, businesses without support in budgeting and marketing often struggled. They stressed that pairing finance with training is essential for long-term success. Bauer, Schmid, and Weber (2022) highlighted regulatory complexity and high compliance costs in Germany's KfW Mikrofinanzfonds, which delayed loans and strained MFI operations. Though simplified applications and advisory services improved repayment and exports, overlapping rules and inefficiencies remained a challenge.

Rhyne and Otero (2021), in Latin America conducted a comparative study to analyze institutional challenges in achieving both profitability and outreach among MFIs, using longitudinal performance data. Their findings revealed that overemphasis on financial sustainability often diverted MFIs from their social mission, especially in competitive markets. The study recommended impact based performance metrics and social auditing frameworks. Supporting studies by Hartarska et al. (2006) and Kinde (2012), found that sound governance and internal controls directly improved performance.

Mrindoko and Pastry (2022) pointed out major transparency problems in Tanzania's microfinance sector. They found that unclear loan terms and low financial literacy often led to poor money management and late repayments. Jabang (2024) stressed the need to educate borrowers and recommended setting up clear, structured financial training and honest loan disclosures to help build trust and improve repayment. Looking at a broader regional picture, Fadikpe et al. (2022) studied MFIs in Ghana, Nigeria, Kenya, and Uganda. They found that poor internal systems, lack of accountability, and loan products that didn't fit clients' needs were major reasons behind high levels of unpaid loans.

Mwansa and Chanda (2023), in a study of microfinance institutions in Lusaka and Kitwe, found that poor coordination between the Bank of Zambia and MFI networks caused confusion in how these institutions operated. They also pointed out that without a shared credit information system, default rates remained high and investor trust stayed low. To solve this, they suggested creating digital databases and stronger ties between MFIs and commercial banks. Chisala and Chileshe (2020) added that high running costs, weak oversight, and low financial literacy among clients made it hard for MFIs to reach more people. In contrast, Banda and Chilufya (2022) believed that many of these issues could be eased by teaching clients how to manage money and by using digital credit tools to make lending more efficient and stable.

3. Methodology

This study used a case study design with a mixed methods with a quantitative approach to assess how well microfinance institutions support the sustainability of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Mtendere East, Lusaka. The target group included SMEs and one MFI operating in the area.

A purposive sample of 31 participants, 30 SMEs and 1 MFI, was selected based on saturation principles. Data was collected from both primary and secondary sources.

Structured questionnaires were used to gather primary data, while secondary information came from institutional reports, government documents, and academic publications. Triangulation helped confirm the accuracy of findings.

Data analysis was done using SPSS version 27 and MegaStat version 9.4, applying frequency tables, chi-square tests, and ANOVA.

Key limitations included limited generalizability, potential response bias, and underreporting of financial issues by SMEs.

Ethical practices were followed, including voluntary participation and strict confidentiality of personal and sensitive information.

4. Presentation of Research Findings and Discussion of Results

This chapter presents the findings conducted in Lusaka's Mtendere East, in line with the thematic objectives of the study. This chapter further discusses the results of the study as well as the existing literature reviewed in chapter 2, so as to find any correlation or opposition in findings.

4.1 Presentation of results on background characteristics of SMEs and MFI

This section presents the Type of business, Size of the business and Proportion of SME clients for MFI.

4.1.1 Type of Business

SMEs reported type of business as is shown in figure 2

Figure 2 Type of business

The bar chart illustrates the type of businesses contacted, with retail comprising the largest group at 43.3% of enterprises, followed by services with 23.3% and both manufacturing and wholesale with 16.7% each. This suggests the retail sector forms the backbone of Small and Medium Enterprises activity in Mtendere East, reflecting a consumer-driven environment where trade and services dominate over production.

4.1.2 Size of the Business

SMEs reported business size as follows in figure 3.

Figure 3 Size of the Business

Figure 3 shows that 77% of micro enterprises employed between one and ten workers, while 23% were small businesses with eleven to fifty workers. This reflects the small-scale nature of entrepreneurship in Mtendere East and the relevance of microfinance institutions. Smaller firms often face greater barriers to accessing formal financial services, pointing to the need for tailored financial support that matches the scale of these businesses.

4.1.3 Proportion of SME Clients MFI Serves

Portion of SME clients MFI serves as shown as in table 1.

Table 1: SMEs served by MFIs
What proportion of your clients are SMEs?

	N	%
less than 25%	1	100.0%

In Table 1, the institution reported that less than 25% of its clients are SMEs, suggesting limited engagement with this segment despite its relevance to financial inclusion. This may reflect either a narrow targeting strategy or low uptake of services by SMEs. It highlights an opportunity to expand outreach and tailor products to better serve this Segment.

4.2 Accessibility of Microfinance Institution (MFIs) Services by Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs).

Under this the following results were taken into consideration, Access to microfinance services, Loan processing time and Chi-Square significance test between Distance to nearest Microfinance Institution and Access to Microfinance Services.

4.2.1 Access to Microfinance Services

SMEs report access to microfinance services as shown in table 2.

Table 2 Ease of accessing microfinance services

	N	%
difficult	11	36.7%
Easy	16	53.3%
very easy	3	10.0%

Table 2 illustrates the findings on the Access of Microfinance Services among Small and Medium Enterprises of Lusaka’s Mtendere East. The findings indicate 53.3% of SMEs found access to Microfinance Services Easy, while 36.7% found it Difficulty and 10% found it Very Easy. This suggests that accessing microfinance services in Lusaka’s Mtendere east is a straightforward process.

4.2.2 Loan Processing Time

SMEs reported loan processing time as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Time taken to receive Loan

	N	%
1-2 weeks	16	53.3%
3-4 weeks	6	20.0%
less than 1 week	7	23.3%
more than 1 month	1	3.3%

Table 3 illustrates the findings on Loan processing time. A 53.3% of SMEs reported they received their loans within a period of 1-2 weeks, 23.3% reported less than a week, 20% reported within a period of 3-4 weeks and only 3.3% reported delays of more than a month. The distribution of loan indicate that the majority of SMEs benefited from the relatively quick access to funds.

4.2.3 Chi-Square significance test between Distance to nearest MFIs and Access to Microfinance Services.

The chi-square significance test between distance to nearest microfinance institution and access to microfinance services was as shown in table 4.

Table 4: Statistical Significant Test

		Access to Microfinance Services				Total
		Very easy	Easy	Difficult	Very difficult	
Less than 1km	Observed	2	3	1		6
	Expected	0.60	3.20	1.80	0.40	6.00
1 to 5km	Observed	1	10	2		13
	Expected	1.30	6.93	3.90	0.87	13.00
6 to 10km	Observed		3	2	1	6
	Expected	0.60	3.20	1.80	0.40	6.00
More than 10km	Observed			4	1	5
	Expected	0.50	2.67	1.50	0.33	5.00
Total	Observed	3	16	9	2	30
	Expected	3.00	16.00	9.00	2.00	30.00
		17.45	chi-square			
		9	df			
		.0421	p-value			
		.763	Phi coefficient			
		.606	Coefficient of Contingency			
		.440	Cramér's V			

Table 4 The Chi-square test established a significant relationship between distance to the nearest microfinance institution and access to microfinance services, ($\chi^2 = 17.45$, $df = 9$ and $p = 0.0421$). These finding emphasized that closer proximity of Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) to Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) leads to more services acquired. This is further indicated by the Strength in association of the Phi coefficient (.763), Coefficient of Contingency (.606) and Cramér's V (.440).

4.3 The Effects of Microfinance Institution (MFIs) Support on the performance of SMEs.

Write Under this section the following results were considered, improved business operations and Chi-Square Significance test between Improved business operations and ANOVA analysis on the Improved Financial Managements Practices and Change in profit after Microfinance support.

4.3.1 Improved Business Operations

SMEs noted improved business operations as presented by table 5.

Figure 4 Improved Business Operations

Figure 4 illustrates a reported 93.3% of Small and Medium Enterprises in Lusaka’s Mtendere East had improved business operations after receiving Microfinance services while only 6.7% reported the opposite. This indicated a significant impact that microfinance services have contributed to the small and medium enterprises of Lusaka’s Mtendere East.

4.3.2 Chi-Square Significance Test Between Improved Business Operations And New Customers Gained

A Chi-Square Significance test between improved business operations and new customers gained was presented below in table 6.

Table 5: Statistical Significant Test Improved Business Operations

		Number of new Customers after implementing Microfinance Services				Total	values not counted
		>30	30-50	50-100	>100		
Improvements to your Business Operations	Yes	Observed	1	10	8	9	28
	Expected	1.93	9.66	7.72	8.69	28.00	
No	Observed	1					1
	Expected	0.07	0.34	0.28	0.31	1.00	
Total	Observed	2	10	8	9	29	
	Expected	2.00	10.00	8.00	9.00	29.00	
		13.98	chi-square				
		3	df				
		.0029	p-value				
		.694	Phi coefficient				
		.570	Coefficient of Contingency				
		.694	Cramér's V				

Table 5 the Chi-square test established a significant relationship between business operations and new customers gained after microfinance implementation, ($\chi^2 = 13.98$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.0029$). Findings demonstrate microfinance driven operational

improvements strongly enhanced customer acquisition. This was further reinforced by the strength of association in the Phi coefficient (.694), Coefficient of Contingency (.570) and Cramér's V (.694).

4.3.3 One-way ANOVA analysis between the Improved Financial Managements Practices and Change in profit after Microfinance support.

A one way ANOVA analysis between the improved financial management practices and change in profit after microfinance support was presented in table 7.

Table 6: Statistical Test for Difference

r ²	0.008
Adjusted r ²	0.000
r	0.090
Std. Error	0.638
n	30
k	1
Dep. Var.	profit percentage after Implementing microfinance

ANOVA table					
Source	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Regression	0.0926	1	0.0926	0.23	.6373
Residual	11.4074	28	0.4074		
Total	11.5000	29			

Regression output				confidence interval		
variables	coefficients	std. error	t (df=28)	p-value	95% lower	95% upper
Intercept	1.2963	0.4429	2.927	.0067	0.3891	2.2035
Improvements to Financial Management Practices	0.1852	0.3884	0.477	.6373	0.6105	0.9809

Table 6 The regression results show that improvements in financial management practices have no significant effect on profit percentage after microfinance implementation ($\beta = 0.1852$, $t(28) = 0.477$, $p = .6373$). The model explains only 0.8% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.008$), and the confidence interval (-0.6105 to 0.9809) confirms the effect is weak and unreliable. The ANOVA test ($F(1,28) = 0.23$, $p = .6373$) also shows the model is not statistically significant. Although the intercept is significant, the independent variable does not contribute meaningfully to explaining changes in profit.

4.4 Challenges Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) Encounter in Rendering Services to Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs).

Under this section the following considered, Tailored products to SMEs, Hindrances to obtaining MFI services and Suggestions for Improvements.

4.4.1 Tailored products to SMEs

SME responses to tailored products covered by MFI was as reported in table 7.

Table 7: MFIs tailor products to SME needs

	N	%
no	12	40.0%
yes	18	60.0%

Table 8 The findings revealed a reported 60% of SMEs within Lusaka's Mtendere East believed Microfinance Institution (MFIs) tailored their products to meet the specific needs of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) while 40% reported the opposite. The majority responses suggested that most SMEs had either experienced or observed some level of customization in Microfinance offerings while the later felt their offerings did not quite meet with their business realities. The results reflected a moderately positive perception of product tailoring, with room for improvement in aligning microfinance services more closely with SME needs.

4.4.2 Hindrances in obtaining MFI services

SMEs noted limitations in getting services from microfinance institutions presented in table 9.

Table 9: Hindrance in obtaining MFI services

	N	%
high interest rates	13	43.3%
not aware of microfinance institutions	3	10.0%
poor credit history	9	30.0%
slow processing time	5	16.7%

Table 9 Revealed Barriers that SMEs and MFIs perceive as hindrances when obtaining Microfinance services. The findings showed 43.3% of SMEs reported High interest rates, 30% reported Poor credit history, 16.7% report slow processing time and 10% reported Not aware of Microfinance Institutions. These findings suggest the Financial and Informational Barriers to be addressed in order to enhance and effectively utilize these services both for SMEs and MFIs.

4.4.3 Suggestions to Improve MFI Services

SME suggestions to improve MFI services was as shown in the table 10 below.

Table 10: Suggestions to improve MFI services

	N	%
faster processing time	6	20.0%
lower interest rates	10	33.3%
more financial training	1	3.3%
reduced documentation	2	6.7%
tailored SME products	11	36.7%

Table 10 Findings showed key SME suggestions for improving MFI services. The most common was tailoring products to SME needs 36.7%, followed by lower interest rates 33.3% and faster processing times 20%. Other recommendations included reduced documentation 6.7% and financial training 3.3%. The results highlighted the need for responsive, SME-focused microfinance to support business growth and sustainability. Strengthening these areas enhances SME performance and expands the reach of MFIs, creating a more inclusive financial environment that drove long-term economic development.

4.5 Discussion of Research Findings

This section discusses the findings to the research at hand. It evaluates Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) on the sustainability of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Lusaka’s Mtendere East. It follows the thematic Area of discussion.

4.5.1 Accessibility of Microfinance services by Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Lusaka’s Mtendere East.

The study reported that 53.3% SMEs in Mtendere East of Lusaka found access to microfinance services easy while 36.7% said it was difficult and 10% very easy. Most SMEs received the funds within two weeks, with only 3.3% of the sample encountering a delay of over a month as the loan processing frames were quite favourable. Statistical evaluation with the chi-square test revealed a significant association between distance to nearest micro-finance institution and ease of access, ($\chi^2 = 17.45$, $df = 9$, $p = 0.0421$). Thus distance plays an important role in ease of access. It is clear from these findings that MFIs are present and are somewhat effective in extending services, but due to geography and way of doing things access to the SME’S is not equitable in Mtendere East.

The findings of this study are consistent with those of Phiri and Nkolola (2018), which showed that borrower education, proximity and past repayment experience significantly improves access to microfinance by SMEs in Lusaka. Just like the previous one, Saïdi (2022) and Daka (2023) claim that high-interest rates, collateral requirements, and complex application procedures are still barriers in the presence of MFIs. As noted in an international context by Jalhare (2025) and Cull et al. (2022), outreach and regional customization are necessary for inclusive access. The case of Mtendere East reveals that the immediate barriers are physical distance and delays in loan processing; unlike studies in India and Morocco which found regulatory reforms and digital inclusion to be key enablers (Chikhaoui & Sobczak, 2021; Mahmoud & Hassan, 2023). The difference shows localized solutions are needed to address both issues and lack of capacity.

4.5.2 Effects of MFIs support on the Financial Performance of SMEs in Lusaka’s Mtendere East.

According to the study, findings revealed 93.3% of SMEs in Mtendere East experienced operational improvement after receiving support from MFIs. Over half 53.3% accessed loans within one to two weeks, while 23.3% secured financing in under a week, indicating relatively efficient loan disbursement. A statistically significant relationship was observed between SME operational improvement and customer acquisition ($\chi^2 = 13.98$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.0029$, Cramér’s $V = 0.694$), confirming that MFI services contributed to business growth. However, despite 80% of respondents reporting improved financial management practices, regression analysis ($R^2 = 0.008$, $p = 0.6373$) and ANOVA ($F = 0.464$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.633$) revealed no significant link between these practices and changes in profit levels. This suggests that while operational capacity improved, profitability may not have increased without further strategic or advisory input.

These results echo the findings by Mukendi and Manda (2022), who observed that access to credit enhanced cooperative savings and group behavior among women entrepreneurs, but noted that limited business skills reduced long-term outcomes. Moussa (2020) reported a 78% increase in net profit among Lebanese SMEs supported by MFIs, attributing this to loan size and complementary training. In Algeria, Belkacem and Haoues (2023) found that peer monitoring in village banking models boosted repayment and business expansion, highlighting the importance of social capital in MFI success. Conversely, Chitalu and Mwale (2022) argued that high operational costs and weak follow-up mechanisms among Zambian MFIs reduced the effectiveness of MFI support in peri-urban areas. Taken together, these studies reinforce that MFIs can drive business improvement, but long-term financial impact depends heavily on additional services like mentorship, training and strong institutional support.

4.5.3 Discussion of Findings on the Challenges Faced by MFIs in Rendering Services to SMEs

The study found that microfinance institutions in Mtendere East face several key challenges when serving SMEs. These include high interest rates, long loan processing periods, low repayment discipline, poor borrower credit history, and a lack of transparency around loan terms. While 80% of SMEs reported receiving financial advice, 43.3% still indicated that unclear loan procedures made it hard to fully utilize the funds. The absence of digital credit systems and limited post-loan follow-up were also noted, suggesting that MFIs struggle not only with resource limitations but also with process inefficiencies and weak client support systems. Respondents recommended digitalizing application procedures, lowering interest rates, and offering tailored financial education to improve MFI performance and SME outcomes.

These challenges reflect broader issues identified in both regional and global studies. Mrindoko and Pastry (2022) reported that transparency failures and low financial literacy in Tanzania led to loan mismanagement and repayment delays. Peterson and Martinez (2021), studying CDFIs in the U.S. Midwest, found that without non-financial support services, access to credit alone did not lead to sustained business growth. Similarly, Bauer et al. (2022) highlighted how complex regulations and inefficiencies in Germany's KfW Mikrofinanzfonds reduced MFI responsiveness and scaled-up impact. Clarke and Jones (2023) added that governance mismatches and the absence of impact reporting tools hindered the effectiveness of socially driven microfinance programs in the UK. In Zambia, Mwansa and Chanda (2023) emphasized that poor coordination between regulators and MFIs created policy uncertainty, while Chisala and Chileshe (2020) pointed to high operational costs and limited financial literacy as barriers to outreach. These findings echo the challenges observed in Mtendere East and highlight the need for better systems, client education, and regulatory alignment to strengthen microfinance service delivery.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

This study evaluated the effectiveness of Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) on the sustainability of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Lusaka's Mtendere East. The findings demonstrated that while a majority of SMEs found microfinance services accessible and reported improved operational performance, persistent structural and institutional challenges limit the overall impact. Access to MFIs was notably influenced by proximity, with most loans disbursed in under two weeks. However, high interest rates and complex application processes remained major barriers.

Operational improvements such as increased customer acquisition and enhanced business practices were observed. Yet, statistical analysis revealed no significant correlation between improved financial management and profit change, indicating that access to finance alone is insufficient for long-term profitability. Furthermore, MFIs faced several challenges in service delivery, including poor borrower credit history, low financial literacy, and a lack of tailored loan products. These were compounded by gaps in transparency, digital infrastructure, and coordination with regulatory bodies.

In line with existing research, the study confirmed that microfinance can contribute to SME growth, especially when accompanied by supportive services such as training and mentorship. However, institutional inefficiencies, resource constraints, and weak governance frameworks continue to restrict outreach and impact. Addressing these issues is essential for MFIs to fulfill their development potential and sustainably support SMEs in Zambia's peri-urban communities.

5.2 Recommendations

To improve the effectiveness of Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) in supporting Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), several measures should be implemented. MFIs need to simplify and digitalize loan applications to reduce delays and enhance accessibility, especially for SMEs with limited documentation. Interest rate policies should be revised to introduce flexible, performance-based models that make borrowing more affordable. Integrating financial literacy into microfinance services is also crucial, as many SMEs lack basic business management skills. Structured training in budgeting, record-keeping, and planning can improve loan utilization and reduce defaults. Additionally, post-loan support through regular follow-ups and advisory services should be institutionalized to help SMEs sustain growth. A centralized digital credit database developed in collaboration with regulators would strengthen credit assessments and minimize repeated defaults. Internally, MFIs should reinforce governance and reporting structures to improve transparency and align with financial inclusion goals. Finally, strategic partnerships with commercial banks can expand funding options and enable MFIs to reach more underserved businesses.

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